

**TRANSLATION PROBLEMS OF ENGLISH VERB INFINITIVE
INTO RUSSIAN**

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Abstract: The article is devoted to the research of grammatical transformations which arise as a result of translation of the for-to-Infinitive Construction from English into Russian. The construction we are considering is the secondary predication construction, whose existence in the sentence demonstrates the implicit predication, which indicates the semantic complexity of the simple sentence. The high frequency of using of such structures in English language allows to implement the compression of the complex sentence and the function of language economy. The article focuses on the transformations of the for-to-Infinitive Construction while translating from English into Russian. The research is based on English articles selected for a study by sampling method based on the criterion of the Infinitive construction under study. Throughout the investigation we have found out that in most cases the English simple sentence maintains its structure while being translated into Russian, but in other cases we can observe a syntactic replacement of a simple sentence by a complex one.

Key words: language, lexical, grammatical sources, translating, infinitive

Source language and target language texts differ formally due to a number of reasons of both objective and subjective character. Objective reasons are caused by the divergence in the language systems and speech models. Subjective reasons can be attributed to the speaker's choice of a language form. Thus, systemic dissimilarity of forms takes place when one of the languages lacks some grammar category and, therefore, has no corresponding form. For example, English possesses the morphological categories of the article or the gerund lacking in the Russian language; whereas in Russian there is a category of adverbial participle (депричастие) missing in the English language. To translate these forms, one has to compensate them or restructure the sentence. Unique categories in one of the languages can occur at the syntactic level as well. For example, English absolute constructions, complex object and complex subject (with the infinitive and participle), are alien to the Russian language. Therefore, they require special attention from students of English. The challenges in translating the English infinitive are due to its specific forms, functions and structures.

Various research in the field of scientific and technical translation is an actual task aimed at the adequacy of translation. It promotes the acceleration of information exchange in the field of the latest developments of science and technology among the experts and scientists from different countries. Scientific and technical texts have some lexical and grammatical features. At the lexical level completeness of translation is reached with the help of terms and presentation of their adequate equivalents which provide clarity and unambiguity of the statement. Grammatical features of English technical and scientific texts, for example, are represented in two features of passive verbal transformation due to the lack of case change of a noun that makes the forms of a direct and indirect object identical and allows passive verbal transformations, using a direct or indirect objects. In the Russian language the direct object is expressed by a noun or a pronoun in the accusative case. Transformation of an active verb form into passive is possible only with the transformation of a direct object into the subject.

In English sentences from technical and scientific texts pronouns they and one are used without pointing to the performer of action. In Russian there is no pronoun in such sentences, an action is transferred by a verb in the third person plural, making a sentence indefinite-personal. In the Russian language the higher degree of abstractness characterizes the 3rd person form of a verb, for example: Scientific and technical style of Russian, as we know, uses almost only this form of a verb. The 1st person form of a verb is applied not very often in scientific and technical texts. But when used we can find only the 1st person plural. It is also in the generalized meaning of some uncertain set of persons where the person of speaker is included. The scientific and technical speech of Russian is characterized by the so-called, «nominative system» - an increase of a share of names and reduction of a share of verbs: first place is won by nouns, the second - by adjectives, and the third - by verbs. The specific feature of the nouns with the meaning of material in scientific and technical style is the possibility of their use in plural for designation of types, grades, substances, tools (oils, fats, sands, dividers, jointers).

Unlike Russian, the English language possesses a number of forms of the same verb: the Simple infinitive, the Continuous infinitive, the Perfect infinitive, the Perfect Continuous infinitive. The first two forms indicate actions simultaneous with that of the main predicate: Я рада, что вижу вас. – I am glad to see you. Я рада, что читаю эту книгу. – I am glad to be reading the book, or the future actions: Я рада, что пойду туда. – I am glad to go there. The Perfect and Perfect

Continuous infinitives denote actions prior to that of the predicate: Я рада, что увидела вас. - I am glad to have seen you. Я рада, что читала эту книгу. - I am glad to have been reading the book. On the other hand, the difference between the Simple / Perfect and Continuous / Perfect Continuous forms of the infinitive lies in expressing either a fact (incomplete or completed) or a process, respectively:

рад, что делаю (каждый день) – glad to do (every day)

рад, что делаю сейчас – glad to be doing

рад, что буду делать – glad to do

рад сделать (что сделаю) – glad to do

рад, что сделал – glad to have done

рад, что делал – glad to have been doing.

The actual meaning of the infinitive can be determined by the context only.

English infinitive functions can also be a stumbling block for a fledgling translator. The attributive function of the infinitive can cause difficulties in translation due to its modal meaning: This is a book to read. – Вот книга, которую можно (нужно) почитать. The type of modal meaning can be seen from the context: When nature has work to be done, she creates a genius to do it. (Emerson) – Когда природе предстоит что-то сделать, она создает гения, который может сделать это. However, it is not always necessary to verbalize the modal meaning in Russian: The latest reports from Europol, the organization to be established for the coordination of police work in all the countries of the European Union, indicates that it has not yet been able to agree on a single working language. – В последних докладах Европола, организации, созданной для координации работы полиции во всех странах Европейского Союза, отмечается, что в вопросе о едином рабочем языке согласия еще не достигнуто. As is seen from the examples, the attributive infinitive usually has the meaning of a future action/state.

The function of some adverbial infinitives presents difficulties in translation. For example, the English infinitive can be used to denote a subsequent event or a parallel action, which is often confused with the infinitive of purpose: Iron combines with oxygen to form rust. – Железо соединяется с кислородом и образует ржавчину. The infinitive in this function is usually rendered by a parallel finite verb: (In many rooms, one wall or another was overgrown with black-green mold.) ... In some rooms, the mold grew thickly halfway down a wall, only to stop in a sharp horizontal line, as if cut by a knife. – (Во многих комнатах одна-две стены были покрыты темно-зеленой плесенью)...В

некоторых комнатах плесень густо покрывала полстены, и резко прерывалась, словно ножом была проведена горизонтальная линия.

This infinitive should be distinguished from the infinitive of purpose: Live not to eat, but eat to live. – Живи не для того, чтобы есть, но ешь для того, чтобы жить.

When translating the infinitive of result, a translator should take care to render properly the connotation of the construction: the infinitive with too implies a negative meaning, while the infinitive with enough suggests a positive one: She is too old to go there. – Она слишком стара и не поедет туда. She is old enough to go there. – Она достаточно взрослая и может поехать туда.

Infinitive constructions are the most challenging problem. They are usually translated by a clause. For instance, the Complex Object construction: We expect them to pay us by Friday. – Мы ожидаем, что нам дадут зарплату к пятнице.

When translating the Complex Subject construction, it is recommended that the finite verb be translated first, and then the subject and the infinitive be joined to form a clause: After a few minutes the men were seen to be running in all directions. – Через несколько минут увидели, что эти люди бегут в разные стороны. The letter seems to have been opened. – Кажется, письмо уже вскрыли. The main verb of the sentence is translated with the indefinite or impersonal form (кажется, видели) or with a parenthetical phrase (конечно, по-видимому, очевидно): The reporters were certain to misunderstand his attendance... – Конечно, журналисты неправильно истолковали его присутствие .., or by an introductory phrase (согласно сообщению, как сообщают): The EPO is expected to make a final decision in the near future. – Как ожидают, Европейское патентное ведомство примет решение в ближайшем будущем.

When dealing with the for-to-infinitive construction, a translator substitutes an English simple sentence with a Russian complex one, i.e. s/he does the partitioning of the sentence: She arranged for the office to be opened by one of the security people. – Она устроила так, что офис открыл один из охранников. In some cases this type of construction can be rendered by a compound sentence: He was a very nice fellow, you had only to say you wanted something for him to give it to you. – Он был очень славный малый: стоило вам только сказать, что вам что-то нужно, и он тут же давал это вам.

Special difficulties can arise from the Absolute construction with the infinitive. This construction usually has the meaning either of concession or of successive events: With so much to say, the two said nothing. – И хотя этим двоим так

много надо было сказать, они не сказали ничего. The resolution calls for the withdrawal of Israeli troops from occupied territories, with a peace conference to follow. – В резолюции содержится призыв вывести израильские войска с оккупированных территорий, после чего будет созвана мирная конференция.

To summarize, the ways of translating English infinitives are as follows:

by the infinitive: To err is human. – Человеку свойственно ошибаться.

by the noun: The best way to make children good is to make them happy. – Лучший способ воспитания хороших детей – это сделать их счастливыми.

by the participle: The problem to be considered in Chapter 2 is concerned with the article. – Вопрос, рассматриваемый в главе 2, касается артикля.

by the clause: Вопрос, который будет рассмотрен в главе 2, касается артикля.

by homogeneous, that is, parallel, verbs: He went to Australia to fall sick there. – Он поехал в Австралию и там заболел.

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